

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF USING WIND ENERGY

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Abstract

The demand for energy around the world is growing rapidly, and the widespread use of traditional energy resources leads to global warming, environmental pollution, health problems, etc. reasons. Fossil energy resources are rapidly depleting, and wind energy is a cost-effective and promising source of renewable energy. Resources. Thus, understanding and development of wind energy technologies in the field of green energy production is necessary. Provides an introduction to wind energy conversion systems and the current status and future prospects of wind energy technologies. In addition, this chapter also discusses the socio-economic and environmental issues of wind energy systems.

Keywords: Wind energy, energy resources, wind turbines, turbine efficiency, alternator.

Introduction:

Wind energy has been used for a long time. The first windmill used to generate electricity was built in 1888.

At the top of a fairly tall support tower is a wind turbine consisting of large blades. When the wind hits the turbine blades, the turbine rotates according to the design and arrangement of the rotor blades. The turbine shaft is connected to an electric generator. The output power of the generator is collected through power cables.

In 2020, wind energy will provide about 1,600 kilowatt-hours of electricity. At first, people used these sailing ships powered by the wind. Wind energy is then used to grind grain and pump water from underground water wells or wells [2]. In 1887, the first windmill generating electricity was built in Scotland. The 1973 oil crisis initiated changes in wind energy research. Currently, the capacity factor in wind energy production is not stable, in some countries it decreases and increases. China ranks first in wind energy production with a capacity of 155 megawatts. Wind energy is completely renewable and does not pollute the environment. And operating costs are very low. The land used for wind farms is also used for agriculture. Wind energy forecasts are possible, but forecasts are only made for short periods of time. The most suitable places for wind power plants are sea coasts. The wind energy industry has experienced tremendous growth in recent years. The increase is mainly aimed at the growing market, higher economic conditions for wind energy due to political choices, and the development of giant wind turbines and offshore farms [3]. The goal is to increase turbine reliability. The topic is relevant even for marine farms, where maintenance is complex and expensive. Maintenance management plays a central role in the wind energy sector.

Wind is a clean, renewable energy source and one of the most cost-effective sources of electricity. On the other hand, wind turbines can be noisy and aesthetically unattractive, and sometimes have a negative impact on the physical environment around them. Like solar energy, wind energy is intermittent, meaning turbines are

dependent on weather conditions and therefore cannot produce electricity 24 hours a day, 7 days a week.

Wind energy is clean and renewable energy. Unlike coal, natural gas or oil, generating electricity from wind does not produce greenhouse gas emissions. Although there are some environmental considerations when building large wind farms, once in operation wind turbines do not need to burn fossil fuels to operate.

In addition, wind energy is completely renewable and will never run out. Unlike traditional fossil fuel reserves, which are replenished very slowly, wind occurs naturally in our atmosphere and we don't have to worry about future supply problems.

Wind power has low operating costs. In terms of upfront costs, wind farms or individual turbines can be expensive to install. However, once operational, operating costs will be relatively low; their fuel (wind) is free and the turbines require little maintenance during their lifetime. A clean future will involve a mix of energy sources, including renewables such as wind power. Wind is generated by the uneven heating of the earth's surface by the sun due to the Earth's rotation and geographic features. Warm air rises, creating areas of low pressure, and cold air sinks, creating areas of high pressure. Air molecules typically move from areas of high pressure to areas of low pressure, creating what we experience as wind.

Using wind as energy is an idea that has been around for thousands of years. Because it does not involve burning a limited amount of fossil fuels, and the use of wind energy does not reduce the amount of wind, it is considered a renewable energy source. Although wind energy has its advantages and disadvantages, wind energy plays a valuable role in a clean electricity grid.

To generate wind energy, the kinetic energy of the wind is used to generate mechanical energy. A generator to use this energy for the benefit of humanity is converted into electricity. Recently, various types of electricity generation have become a frequent topic of discussion among experts. Undoubtedly, wind energy is one of the harbingers of technological advances that

can lead to more efficient energy production. At first glance, the future of wind energy looks promising.

Wind energy is more obvious. The main benefits include the unlimited, free, renewable resource (wind itself), economic value, maintenance costs and placement of wind turbines. First of all, wind is an unlimited, free and renewable resource. Wind is a natural phenomenon, and harvesting kinetic energy from the wind has no effect on currents or wind cycles. Additionally, wind energy harvesting is a clean and non-polluting way to generate electricity. Unlike other types of power plants, it does not emit any pollutants or greenhouse gases into the air. Wind turbines generate electricity from harmless tailwinds. Wind energy is much more environmentally friendly than burning fossil fuels to generate electricity. Currently The US, like other countries, remains dependent on fossil fuel imports from unstable and unreliable countries. [1] (Fossil fuel) supply tensions will increase the price of fossil fuel resources and expose the U.S. economy to international market volatility. Wind energy has the potential to free the United States from the metaphorical economic slavery of fossil fuels. Once the turbines and energy centers are installed, the cost of maintaining the turbines and generating wind energy will be virtually zero. Another advantage of wind energy is the ability to place turbines where needed. Once experts do their research and find places with enough wind, they can place the turbines in the right places. These areas are usually uninhabited (eg offshore wind turbines). [1] In fact, offshore winds tend to blow stronger and more uniformly than on land, providing the potential for increased power production and smoother, more stable operation than onshore wind energy systems.

Disadvantages of wind energy – wind energy is not constant. The efficiency of a wind turbine in producing electricity depends on weather conditions; Thus, it can be difficult for wind to predict exactly how much electricity a turbine will produce over time. If on any given day the wind speed is too low, the turbine rotor will not spin.

This means that wind energy is not always available for use during periods of high electricity demand. To harness only wind energy, wind turbines must be combined with some kind of energy storage technology.

Wind energy causes noise and visual pollution. One of the biggest negative aspects of wind energy is noise and visual pollution. Wind turbines can be noisy to operate due to both the mechanical operation and the wind vortices created as they rotate blades. Additionally, since wind turbines must be built tall enough to capture strong enough winds, turbines are often located near mountain ranges, lakes, oceans, etc., which can reduce scenic views.

Wind turbine blades are very large and rotate at very high speeds. Unfortunately, their blades can harm and kill species that fly towards them, such as birds and bats. If wind farms are not built in an environmentally sustainable manner, it could also disrupt the natural habitats of native species. However, these problems can be overcome to some extent with technological advances and properly designed wind farms.

Wind energy requires transmission. In many cases, turbines and production sites may be located quite far from residential areas where power is required. Therefore, transmission lines are an additional piece of infrastructure that must be built for this type of power generation to be successful.

The two main disadvantages of wind energy are the initial cost and the immaturity of the technology. First, turbines and wind turbines are very expensive to build. The second drawback is the immaturity of technology. [1] High energy costs can be partially addressed through technological innovations that improve reliability and energy production and reduce system capital costs. Offshore wind produces more energy than onshore wind, but is more expensive to build. The main costs of wind turbines include construction and maintenance. [1] Reducing costs, new technologies are needed to improve reliability and energy production, address regional deployment challenges, expand resource space, develop infrastructure and production capacity, and reduce known impacts on environment. Therefore, it can be argued that the introduction of wind energy should be delayed until technological progress is achieved. Other disadvantages include:

Many people are interested in the visual effects that wind turbines create in beautiful natural landscapes. They believe the huge wind turbines distract viewers from the beautiful surroundings.

Wind turbines can be dangerous to flying animals. Many birds and bats were killed by flying into the rotors. Experts are currently conducting research to learn more about the impact of wind turbines on marine habitats.

While this can be an advantage (locating wind turbines in uninhabited areas, away from people), it can also be a disadvantage. Transport and maintenance costs for turbines add up and take time. Offshore wind turbines require a boat to operate and can be dangerous to operate.

Some wind turbines produce a lot of noise, which can be unpleasant.

This is a safety device at sea. In the dark, it can be difficult for boats arriving at night to see wind turbines, which can lead to collisions.

Perhaps the biggest disadvantage of wind power is that it cannot be produced continuously. Energy will only be produced when the wind blows.

The amount of energy produced by turbines also depends on wind speed. Thus, wind energy is not very suitable as a source of base load energy, which is our main source of electricity production.

However, as energy storage technology continues to become more cost-effective, it may become possible to become more dependent on wind power. IN currently, due to their unreliability, wind turbines have to be used in combination with other energy sources to meet our electricity needs.

The efficiency of a wind turbine can vary depending on a number of factors, such as its design, location, and the average wind speed in that area.

In general, modern wind turbines can achieve conversion efficiencies of around 30-45%, increasing to

50% during periods of peak wind load. This is considered a good thing - if a wind turbine operated at 100% efficiency, the wind would die out completely after passing through the blades.

The result.

Wind power is one of the fastest growing renewable energy technologies.

However, given the growing demand for wind energy, it should be noted that current wind energy technologies are still far from optimal.

Due to its intermittent nature, wind energy poses significant new challenges to becoming a fully reliable technology. For example, on average modern wind turbines operate at only 35% of their capacity. They also operate at full capacity less than 10% of the time.

This is due in part to wind variability, but also to economic factors that influence the aerodynamic design of wind turbines. Although it is possible to increase wind energy capture by increasing the rotor diameter, this approach has economic limitations.

The intermittent and unpredictable nature of wind power makes energy storage systems a key element of renewable energy.

Renewable energy sources such as wind could play an important role in the world's energy future. The next generation of wind turbines should improve their efficiency, reduce acquisition costs, improve the reliability and cost of electricity produced, and make them more competitive with traditional fossil fuels.

The benefits of wind energy far outweigh the disadvantages. Gradually, myths about wind generation are being dispelled and a bright future can be predicted for wind energy in general.

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